

ON THE NUMBER OF PRIMES FOR WHICH
A POLYNOMIAL IS EISENSTEIN

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Abstract

Previously Heyman and Shparlinski gave an asymptotic formula with error term for the number of Eisenstein polynomials of fixed degree and bounded height. Let $\psi(f)$ denote the number of primes for which a polynomial f is Eisenstein. We give expressions for the mean and variance of the function ψ for each fixed degree, where the polynomials are ordered according to their height.

1. Introduction

For an integer $d \geq 2$, let $f(x) = a_d x^d + a_{d-1} x^{d-1} + \cdots + a_1 x + a_0$ be a polynomial with integer coefficients. We say that f is Eisenstein if there exists a prime p such that $p \mid a_i$ for $i = 0, 1, \dots, d-1$, $p^2 \nmid a_0$, and $p \nmid a_d$. The well-known fact that Eisenstein polynomials are irreducible is often encountered in an undergraduate algebra course. See [1] for a fascinating history of this result, which was proved independently by Schönemann and Eisenstein.

Dobbs and Johnson (see [2]) posed some probabilistic questions concerning Eisenstein polynomials. In particular, one could ask: What is the probability that a

randomly chosen polynomial is Eisenstein? Dubickas answers this question in [4] by providing an asymptotic expression for the number of monic Eisenstein polynomials of fixed degree and bounded height. Later Heyman and Shparlinski (see [6]) gave an asymptotic expression for the number of Eisenstein polynomials (monic or not) of fixed degree and bounded height but with a stronger error term. We mention in passing that there are generalizations and variations one may consider; some results in this area include [5, 7, 8, 3].

Our paper builds naturally on [6] so we begin by stating their result. Define the height of a polynomial f to be $\max\{|a_0|, |a_1|, \dots, |a_d|\}$. Let $\mathcal{F}_d(H)$ be the set of Eisenstein polynomials of degree d and height at most H .

Theorem 1 (Heyman–Shparlinski). *We have*

$$\#\mathcal{F}_d(H) = \gamma_d(2H)^{d+1} + \begin{cases} O(H^d) & \text{if } d > 2 \\ O(H^2(\log H)^2) & \text{if } d = 2. \end{cases}$$

Let $\psi(f)$ denote the number of primes for which f is Eisenstein. Our aim is to study the statistics of this function. We establish the following result, which gives an expression for the mean and variance of the function $\psi(f)$ as f ranges over all Eisenstein polynomials of a fixed degree.

Theorem 2. *Let*

$$\alpha_d := \sum_{p \text{ prime}} \frac{(p-1)^2}{p^{d+2}}, \quad \beta_d := \sum_{p \text{ prime}} \left(\frac{(p-1)^2}{p^{d+2}} \right)^2$$

and

$$\gamma_d := 1 - \prod_{p \text{ prime}} \left(1 - \frac{(p-1)^2}{p^{d+2}} \right).$$

Then we have

$$\mu_d := \lim_{H \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_d(H)} \psi(f)}{\sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_d(H)} 1} = \frac{\alpha_d}{\gamma_d},$$

$$\sigma_d^2 := \lim_{H \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_d(H)} (\psi(f) - \mu_d)^2}{\sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_d(H)} 1} = \frac{\alpha_d + \alpha_d^2 - \beta_d - \mu_d \alpha_d}{\gamma_d}.$$

We note in passing that α_d and β_d can be expressed as finite linear combinations of values of the prime zeta function $P(s) = \sum_p p^{-s}$. Throughout this paper, the variables p and q will always denote primes. See Section 3 for additional comments on $\alpha_d, \beta_d, \gamma_d, \mu_d, \sigma_d^2$, including a table of numerical values for various values of d .

2. Proofs

As usual we let $\omega(n)$ denote the number of distinct prime factors of n and let $\phi(n)$ denote the Euler phi-function. Following [6], we let $\mathcal{H}_d(s, H)$ be the number of polynomials of degree d and height at most H satisfying $s \mid a_i$ for $i = 0, 1, \dots, d - 1$, $\gcd(a_0/s, s) = 1$, and $\gcd(a_d, s) = 1$.

Lemma 1. *We have*

$$\#\mathcal{H}_d(s, H) = \frac{(2H)^{d+1}\phi^2(s)}{s^{d+2}} + O\left(\frac{2^{\omega(s)}H^d}{s^{d-1}}\right). \tag{1}$$

Proof. See Lemma 5 of [6]. □

Lemma 2. *We have*

$$\sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_d(H)} \psi(f) = (2H)^{d+1}\alpha_d + \begin{cases} O(H^2) & \text{if } d > 2 \\ O(H^2 \log \log H) & \text{if } d = 2. \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

Proof. We rewrite the sum in question as a sum over primes and apply Lemma 1; this yields

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_d(H)} \psi(f) &= \sum_{p \leq H} \#\mathcal{H}_d(p, H) \\ &= \sum_{p \leq H} \left[\frac{(2H)^{d+1}\phi^2(p)}{p^{d+2}} + O\left(\frac{2^{\omega(p)}H^d}{p^{d-1}}\right) \right] \\ &= (2H)^{d+1} \sum_{p \leq H} \frac{(p-1)^2}{p^{d+2}} + \sum_{p \leq H} O\left(\frac{H^d}{p^{d-1}}\right) \\ &= (2H)^{d+1} \sum_p \frac{(p-1)^2}{p^{d+2}} - (2H)^{d+1} \sum_{p > H} \frac{(p-1)^2}{p^{d+2}} + \sum_{p \leq H} O\left(\frac{H^d}{p^{d-1}}\right). \end{aligned}$$

The splitting of $\sum_{p \leq H}$ into \sum_p and $\sum_{p > H}$ is justified since \sum_p converges absolutely. It remains to bound the second and third terms in the last line above. We bound the second term using the integral test to obtain

$$(2H)^{d+1} \sum_{p > H} \frac{(p-1)^2}{p^{d+2}} = O\left(H^{d+1} \int_H^\infty \frac{(x-1)^2}{x^{d+2}} dx\right) = O(H^{d+1}H^{-d+1}) = O(H^2).$$

For the third term, we find

$$H^d \sum_{p \leq H} \frac{1}{p^{d-1}} = \begin{cases} O(H^2) & \text{if } d > 2 \\ O(H^2 \log \log H) & \text{if } d = 2, \end{cases}$$

where we have used Mertens' Theorem (see, for example, [9]) in the case of $d = 2$. □

Lemma 3. *We have*

$$\sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_d(H)} \psi(f)^2 = (\alpha_d + \alpha_d^2 - \beta_d)(2H)^{d+1} + \begin{cases} O(H^2) & \text{if } d > 2 \\ O(H^2(\log \log H)^2) & \text{if } d = 2. \end{cases}$$

Proof. If we define

$$\tau(f, p) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } f \text{ is } p\text{-Eisenstein} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

then the first sum can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_d(H)} \psi(f)^2 &= \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_d(H)} \left(\sum_{p \text{ prime}} \tau(f, p) \right)^2 \\ &= \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_d(H)} \left(\sum_{p \text{ prime}} \tau(f, p) \sum_{q \text{ prime}} \tau(f, q) \right) \\ &= \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_d(H)} \left(\sum_{p, q \text{ prime}} \tau(f, p) \tau(f, q) \right) \\ &= \sum_{p, q \text{ prime}} \left(\sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_d(H)} \tau(f, p) \tau(f, q) \right). \end{aligned}$$

The inner sum above represents the number of polynomials of height at most H that are Eisenstein for both p and q , but the fact that p may equal q complicates matters. Consequently, we have

$$\sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_d(H)} \psi(f)^2 = \sum_{p \leq H} \#\mathcal{H}(p, H) + \sum_{\substack{pq \leq H \\ p \neq q}} \#\mathcal{H}(pq, H).$$

The first sum on the right-hand side above is exactly what appears in Lemma 2, and therefore is it equal to the right-hand side of (2). It remains to deal with the

second sum, which equals

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{\substack{pq \leq H \\ p \neq q}} \#\mathcal{H}(pq, H) \\ &= (2H)^{d+1} \sum_{\substack{pq \leq H \\ p \neq q}} \frac{(p-1)^2(q-1)^2}{p^{d+2}q^{d+2}} + O\left(\sum_{\substack{p, q \text{ prime} \\ pq \leq H}} \frac{H^d}{(pq)^{d-1}} 2^{\omega(pq)}\right) \\ &= (2H)^{d+1} \sum_{pq \leq H} \frac{(p-1)^2(q-1)^2}{p^{d+2}q^{d+2}} - (2H)^{d+1} \sum_{p^2 \leq H} \left(\frac{(p-1)^2}{p^{d+2}}\right)^2 \\ & \qquad \qquad \qquad + O\left(H^d \sum_{\substack{p, q \text{ prime} \\ pq \leq H}} \frac{1}{(pq)^{d-1}}\right). \end{aligned}$$

For the first term, as in the proof of Lemma 2, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & (2H)^{d+1} \sum_{pq \leq H} \frac{(p-1)^2(q-1)^2}{p^{d+2}q^{d+2}} \\ &= (2H)^{d+1} \sum_{p, q} \frac{(p-1)^2(q-1)^2}{p^{d+2}q^{d+2}} + (2H)^{d+1} \sum_{p > H} \frac{1}{p^d} \sum_{q > H/p} \frac{1}{q^d} \\ &= (2H)^{d+1} \left(\sum_p \frac{(p-1)^2}{p^{d+2}}\right)^2 + O\left(H^{d+1} \sum_{p > H} \frac{1}{p^d}\right) \\ &= (2H)^{d+1} \alpha_d^2 + O(H^2). \end{aligned}$$

For the second term,

$$\begin{aligned} & (2H)^{d+1} \sum_{p^2 \leq H} \left(\frac{(p-1)^2}{p^{d+2}}\right)^2 \\ &= (2H)^{d+1} \sum_p \left(\frac{(p-1)^2}{p^{d+2}}\right)^2 - (2H)^{d+1} \sum_{p > \sqrt{H}} \left(\frac{(p-1)^2}{p^{d+2}}\right)^2 \\ &= (2H)^{d+1} \beta_d + O(H^{3/2}). \end{aligned}$$

Finally, for the third term, we have

$$H^d \sum_{\substack{p, q \text{ prime} \\ pq \leq H}} \frac{1}{(pq)^{d-1}} = \begin{cases} O(H^2), & \text{if } d > 2 \\ O(H^2 (\log \log H)^2), & \text{if } d = 2. \end{cases}$$

Putting this all together proves the lemma. □

Proof of Theorem 2. The part of the theorem concerning the mean μ_d follows immediately from Lemma 2 and Theorem 1. Now we consider the variance:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_d^2 &= \lim_{H \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_d(H)} (\psi(f) - \mu_d)^2}{\sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_d(H)} 1} \\ &= \lim_{H \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\#\mathcal{F}_d(H)} \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_d(H)} (\psi(f)^2 - 2\psi(f)\mu_d + \mu_d^2) \\ &= \lim_{H \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\#\mathcal{F}_d(H)} \left[\sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_d(H)} \psi(f)^2 - 2\mu_d \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_d(H)} \psi(f) + \mu_d^2 \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_d(H)} 1 \right]. \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 2, Lemma 3, and Theorem 1, the limit above equals

$$\frac{1}{\gamma_d} [(\alpha_d + \alpha_d^2 - \beta_d) - 2\mu_d\alpha_d + \mu_d^2\gamma_d],$$

which simplifies to the desired expression. □

3. Remarks on the Constants

It is not hard to show that

$$\alpha_d = \frac{1}{2^{d+2}} + O\left(\frac{1}{3^d}\right), \quad \beta_d = \frac{1}{2^{2(d+2)}} + O\left(\frac{1}{3^{2d}}\right), \quad \gamma_d = \frac{1}{2^{d+2}} + O\left(\frac{1}{3^d}\right).$$

It then follows that $\lim_{d \rightarrow \infty} \mu_d = 1$ and $\lim_{d \rightarrow \infty} \sigma_d^2 = 0$, as one would expect. If one was interested in the mean $\hat{\mu}_d$ and variance $\hat{\sigma}_d^2$ of $\psi(f)$ as f ranges over all polynomials, instead of just Eisenstein polynomials, one would obtain the simpler expressions $\hat{\mu}_d = \alpha_d$ and $\hat{\sigma}_d^2 = \alpha_d - \beta_d$. We will not prove this explicitly but it essentially follows from the proof of Theorem 2. In this case, one observes that $\lim_{d \rightarrow \infty} \hat{\mu}_d = 0$ and $\lim_{d \rightarrow \infty} \hat{\sigma}_d^2 = 0$, as expected.

d	$\alpha_d = \hat{\mu}_d$	β_d	γ_d	μ_d	σ_d^2	$\hat{\sigma}_d^2$
2	0.17971	0.00731	0.16765	1.07192	0.07187	0.17239
3	0.05653	0.00127	0.05557	1.01714	0.01705	0.05525
4	0.02255	0.00027	0.02243	1.00519	0.00517	0.02227
5	0.00989	0.00006	0.00988	1.00169	0.00169	0.00983
6	0.00456	0.00001	0.00456	1.00056	0.00056	0.00454

Table 1: Approximate values of the constants for small d

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